

DEVELOPMENT OF READING CULTURE AMONG YOUNG STUDENTS

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Abstract. *In this article, it is necessary to develop the culture of reading among young readers through clubs and to increase their love for books, the book affects the human psyche, leads a person to spiritual maturity, affects his feelings and certainly gives knowledge, and in addition, it gives pleasure to the reader, sharpens his mind and makes him Opinions and opinions about education are expressed.*

The importance of development of reading in our country, especially the development of reading culture among young students, is emphasized.

Keywords: *literacy, culture, thinking, influence on human psyche, tolerance, library, knowledge, high virtue, spirituality, justice.*

Introduction. Today, in our rapidly developing country, effective work is being done in front of the education system to provide modern education and upbringing to the young generation.

In addition to providing a solid education, it aims to educate young people into people who are not susceptible to various ideological threats and aggressions, who can find strength against them, who can think independently, who have a broad worldview, who live with confidence and purpose in life, and who have high morals are putting. In the successful implementation of such tasks, the goal is to convey the feelings of confidence in the future to the hearts and minds of the students, while the traditions, customs, and national values of our country that have come down to us from our centuries-old ancestors have been glorified. The role of books and reading culture is very important in the formation of high spirituality in the hearts of young readers.

In our independent Uzbekistan, we can see that a number of things have been done to develop and improve the reading culture. During our life there are various changes and innovations. Therefore, changes in people's thinking and life activities are required to be reconsidered and strengthened.

Decree of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev dated January 12, 2017 No. PQ-3271 "On the establishment of a commission for the development of the system of printing and distribution of book products, increase and promotion of book reading and reading culture" and "Book products" dated September 13, 2017 "Decision on the program of comprehensive measures to develop the publishing and distribution system, increase and promote book reading and reading culture, Among them are the decisions of May 12, 2018 "On organizing reading contests among young people in order to widely study and promote the creative heritage of our great scholars, writers and thinkers" is serving. Paragraph 45 of the "Comprehensive program of measures to improve the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" approved by the President's decision "On measures to improve the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" No. and "Yosh Kitabkhan" examination contests are being held all over our country in order to raise their spiritual level.

It is necessary to further develop the culture of reading among young students, to awaken their love for books, and to explain the incomparable role of books in the formation of a person with high potential.

Research materials and methodology

The book is an inextinguishable light that illuminates the paths of human life, a source of happiness that gives meaning to human life, and our most loyal friend who accompanies us in any situation. There is nothing as powerful as a book in improving the spiritual maturity of a person. The book-reader not only helps young people to understand the world, expand their worldview, but also improves their scientific and spiritual worldview, changes it in a positive direction, and teaches them to find a way out of various conflicts in life. A student who has acquired these qualities will acquire spiritual thinking and mature into a mature person. So, the book is our spiritual heritage that strengthens the chain of our generations. It affects the human psyche, leads a person to spiritual perfection, affects his feelings and certainly gives knowledge, and in addition, gives pleasure to the student, sharpens his mind and educates him.

Reading books always invites people to virtue and enlightens them. The importance of books and reading is very important in the formation of high spirituality in the hearts of young students. In our country, attention is paid to the development of reading, especially to the development of reading culture among young students.

The study of works dedicated to the book and the reader allows to emphasize that the book represents the most complex phenomenon among the objects included in the educational activities of elementary school students.

Due to its complexity, the "book" still does not have a single interpretation. As the French writer, literary critic, sociologist Robert Escarpi noted: "Like all living beings, the book does not fit within the strict boundaries of definitions. "No one has yet been able to give a clear and stable definition to it."

Bibliographers distinguish the following definitions, which are most commonly used in connection with the concept of "book":

A book is a means of communication between people, a mass media tool.

A book is a synonym of a literary work, a product of the author's work.

Book - publication - publishing - product of polygraphy activity.

A book is a separate form of publication, different from a newspaper, magazine, booklet, album, etc. The form of a certain constructive organization of book pages...

A book is a form of organization of a written message

What is the main meaning of the book for the pedagogue who forms the reader and for the students who learn the art of independent reading? To solve this question, we turned to the definitions of the book from the point of view of its social importance.

One such concise definition is given by A. Hertsen: "...the experience expressed in writing and made available for general use is a book."

We find such definitions in the definitions of many other great scholars of the past and present who have focused on the book: "interlocutor", "teacher", "torch", "teacher", "friend", "priceless heritage", "world seen through man", "history of peoples", "past experience", "heritage of human mind", "thought ship", "a great miracle discovered by man" - these and similar imaginations acquired from childhood evoke a sense of pride for the person who discovered the book, a sense of reverence in front of the book as a place of storage and a means of conveying the experience accumulated by mankind.

The historical experience of mankind and the mental abilities formed in it are realized not only in the book, but also in "every object created by man - from a hand-held weapon to a modern

electronic computing machine." In this sense, the book is not an exception, it is also a "process of thought realization".

But there are two social experiences and individual thoughts in the book: for the first time - when creating a manuscript - in language, in words, when the writer has an urgent need to make his thoughts the property of a wide circle of people, secondly, it should not be forgotten that it should be done in a purposeful and direct manner and in a subject specially designed to organize a written message addressed to all of us.

As there are many types of education, teaching to read books starts from childhood. Therefore, parents and teachers themselves should be the first role models for students. First of all, the role of the family in the development of a person is incomparable.

All of education's methods and criteria are first of all formed in the family, and in the development of reading culture, the family's kiss is finally elevated. That is why it is better to start reading from the family. Therefore, the family environment and family traditions play an important role in the development of a person. In this case, the parents' moral and spiritual development directly affects the child. They can see themselves reflected in a mirror.

After all, reading, my love for artistic literature, incon encourages the development of spiritual thinking. A person who has a heart for books, a person who is in tune with the literary world, it will be great if he transmits such feelings and virtues to those around him, first of all, to his family. The children of the book-reading parents will also give a different meaning to the book. This in turn leads to interest and aspiration for the treasure of our spirituality. Therefore, it is important for parents to be literate and to be interested in artistic literature in the generation of book readers.

The father and mother start their child on the path, the child follows that path. For this, father and mother should stay awake and call only to the right path. Therefore, before inviting their students to read books, teachers can increase their interest in reading by telling interesting and impressive stories from the books they have read to the students in interesting, role-playing ways. Therefore, since time immemorial, wise men and leaders of enlightenment have urged all people to read books and learn the secret of knowledge and manners from them.

The idea about the complexity of the process of human interaction with the book was more clearly expressed by V. N. Lyakhov. The book is a product of social activity on a huge scale," he writes. A person's relationship with a book is multifaceted and complex...

In the interaction of a person with a book, such deep layers of consciousness and subconsciousness are involved that such complex connections and connections arise that their analysis has not yet been studied by science.

It is possible to continue the comparison of the conflicting opinions about the nature of the love of books and the interest in independent reading by referring to early and more recent studies, but they provide no basis for the conclusion about how "easy" everything is and how "complicated" everything is when the problem of introducing books into human life is studied. does not add. However, as noted earlier, ease is illusory, otherwise the problem would not exist.

And the complexity, from our point of view, is explained by the fact that modern science does not yet have a single and general theory that "covers all possible aspects of human learning... but is undoubtedly on the way to creating it." Of course, pedagogy studies a person (including a child) as a subject of education in general, but the possibilities of realizing its main goal have not yet been sufficiently observed: in each given situation - its activity is directed not only to the

objects that need to be studied, evaluated, and changed again, but also to itself and to others like itself. formation of a person, individuality oriented to optimal communication. In the research dedicated to the formation of independent reading in students, the book is of interest to us as a means of educating the "social person" and self-education, because it reveals to the educated reader through the art of words the subtle nuances of the psyche and human behavior, and thus realizes the true value of other people and oneself. But in order to master this weapon, the student must learn it as a tool under the guidance of a teacher, master it as a separate object of activity that opens the reader to an unlimited and unobstructed possibility of selective communication with the reader, just like himself. Therefore, since a seven-year-old child is an individual, learning books as a means of communication, mastering reading as an opportunity to gain experience accumulated by mankind in the process of historical development, turning this activity into an intellectual ability, and forming a need for books in order to make communication based on choice - all this is education. and are the steps of reading preparation that form the quality of independent reading that we are interested in.

Research results

Today, the role of the book in the path of happiness and perfection of the future generation is incomparable.

A good book increases a person's feelings of respect for national and universal values, encourages goodness and goodness, and increases love for the Motherland.

The book prevents the incon from turning into ignorance.

Nowadays, many people who go around the Internet are caught in the trap of malicious people, they believe in various promises and commit various evil deeds.

But it is as clear as the moon that a person who has read the book will not engage in such vile deeds. A book can make a person forget all his pains and sorrows and heal his pain. It was not for nothing that our president said that "a child who has read one book will lead a child who has watched ten televisions".

Only good thoughts and advanced ideas are created from a person who reads books. He calls people to goodness. It is a purposeful and purposeful organization of free time of the students, protecting them from various negative vices, broadening their spiritual outlook, and awakening their love for books.

It is worth mentioning that during the years of independence, a solid system of creating educational literature for educational institutions and delivering it to students was created in our country, and textbooks and study guides are being published in the languages taught in Uzbekistan. The material and technical base of information-resource and information-library centers is updated, and modern electronic library systems are put into widespread use. The book has a place in the happy, perfect, peaceful and prosperous life of our youth, who are our future successors. A number of projects are being implemented to develop the culture of reading among young students through clubs, among them, to promote national Uzbek literature and the world's best works. Every year, taking into account the demands and wishes of young people, more than 100 best works of Uzbek and world writers are published under the heading "Library of Perfection".

In fact, through the "Kamolot" bookstores established in the regions, they serve to deliver the latest published works to young people, including unorganized youth.

The main goal is to attract young readers to clubs and focus their attention on reading through clubs. Information is given on the effective state-level work carried out today to spread

and promote reading, to increase the love of our students for books, and to increase the moral immunity of the students, as well as the place of the book in society and the attention to it.

Discussion

If we think that books are only a source of knowledge, we will not fully understand its essence. In fact, books help us to be happy, reach great heights during our life, and get out of difficult situations. After all, in any pharmacy, you will not find a drug that will bring a person out of depression and make him strong-willed, patient, and hardworking. But this medicine is a book, in which the reader will find what he is looking for.

The book serves as a source of knowledge, spirituality and enlightenment. The goal is to increase the interest of young people in books in order to develop the culture of reading among young people through clubs.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the main goal of the education system today is to make students who can think creatively and freely, who have a wide worldview, mature into mature personnel in every field, businessmen, scientists who provide the future of our country and contribute to the prosperity of our country with their advanced ideas.

In the process of education and training, a method of using modern technologies was developed to ensure the cooperation of parents, science teachers, class leaders and librarians in developing the interest of young students in reading books, and it was considered necessary to widely implement it in practice. In today's information age, the importance of books and reading is incomparable in raising our young people to be highly moral and virtuous.

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